

ANALYSIS OF ATHEROSCLEROTIC PLAQUE IN CAROTID ARTERIES BY USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS

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Abstract

The main aim of this study was to identify and classify the atherosclerotic plaque components such as lipid core, fibrous and calcified tissue, by applying the Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) on Ultrasound (US) imaging data. The U-Net, SegNet, and Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) architectures for multi-class image segmentation have been applied. Four common classification metrics are considered for one-vs-all quantitative evaluation, including accuracy (ACC), precision (P), recall (R) and F1-score. Our models showed a good accuracy in prediction of lipid core, fibrous and calcified carotid tissue based on US images.

In the era of personalized medicine, plaque image analysis has the potential to extract valuable information about the plaques and thus to identify more accurately the patients at risk of plaque rupture. This type of computational methods can pre-estimate the risk of cardiovascular disease and stratify patients as a high/low risk, detecting the stable and vulnerable atherosclerotic plaques.

Key words: US images, Carotid artery, Atherosclerotic plaque, Convolutional neural networks

1. Introduction

Carotid artery disease is a primary cause of ischaemic cerebrovascular events, such as ischemic stroke and transient ischemic attacks (TIAs). Beside carotid stenosis, identification of atherosclerotic plaque components is essential to pre-estimate the risk of cardiovascular disease and stratify them as a high or low risk [1]. Computer sciences have found an important role in automatic and objective determination of atherosclerotic plaque constituents from imaging data [2]. In aim to identify and classify the atherosclerotic plaque components such as lipid core, fibrous and calcified tissue, this study deals with implementation of different convolutional neural networks (CNNs) on ultrasound (US) imaging data.

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, the U-Net, SegNet, and Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) architectures for multi-class image segmentation task have been applied [2, 3]. The original and annotated US

images were used for model training and testing. The problem of atherosclerotic plaque components segmentation is defined as multiclass segmentation model, where four classes should be detected in images (input image size is 512x512 pixels): background (black area outside the atherosclerotic ring, pixel map “0”), fibrous (yellow color, pixel map “1”), lipid (blue color, pixel map “2”) and calcified (green color, pixel map “3”) areas of annotated plaque components.

For the training phase we performed 100 epochs, with batch size 2. For the optimizers Adadelta, Adam, RMSprop were tested, but the results were pretty much the same. At the end a combination of class weights of [0.2, 2, 3, 3] was used for the model training.

3. Results and Conclusion

Metric which was recorded during the training phase is mean IoU (Intersection over Union). PSPNet showed a good accuracy in prediction of lipid, fibrous and calcified carotid plaque types based on US images, a bit better than other two architectures. In figure 1 the 1st, 2nd and 3rd columns represent the original, manually labelled images, and multi-class prediction results, respectively.

Figure 1. Atherosclerotic plaque zones.

The mean IoU value on test set was equal to 0.47753240176078554, while class wise IoU values for the background, fibrous, lipid and calcified plaques were 0.99153125, 0.58382048, 0.01689708, and 0.31788079, respectively.

The risk stratification of carotid atherosclerotic patients remains challenging due to complexity of the tissue. The study will be extended on identification of additional parameters and to larger patients’ database in order to create more robust model to larger variability applying data mining techniques and US data.

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References

- [1] A. Boi, et al. A survey on coronary atherosclerotic plaque tissue characterization in intravascular optical coherence tomography. *Curr Atheroscler Rep*, 20(7):33, 2018.
- [2] K. Lekadir et al. A Convolutional Neural Network for Automatic Characterization of Plaque Composition in Carotid Ultrasound. *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*, 21(1): 48-55, 2017.
- [3] O. Ronneberger et al. U-Net: Convolutional Networks for Biomedical Image Segmentation, *MICCAI Conference, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 9351. Springer, Cham, 2015.*